

*Tiago Pires*¹

"Medical Anthropology", Institute of Ethnology and
Folklore Studies with Ethnographic Museum,
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
[tiago.pires@iefem.bas.bg]

Maria Eduarda de Freitas Xavier

Department of Occupational Therapy
University of São Carlos
[mariafreitas@estudante.ufscar.br]

Art, Culture, and Psychopathology: An Introduction to the Anti-Asylum Narrative of Brazilian Psychiatrist Nise da Silveira

Abstract: *During the mid-1940s, psychiatrist Nise da Silveira (1905 – 1999) began to challenge psychiatric methods of imprisoning patients and treatments such as lobotomy, electroshock, and insulin therapy. She translated and introduced Jung's theory to Brazil, after meeting him in Switzerland in 1957, where she also presented her work "Schizophrenia in Pictures" at the 2nd International Congress of Psychiatry in Zurich. Nise da Silveira was a pioneer of the process of deinstitutionalizing mental health treatment long before Franco Basaglia's visit and influence in Brazil in the late 1970s. Silveira established the "Occupational Therapy Atelier" at the "Pedro II Psychiatric Center" in Rio de Janeiro in 1946, as well as the "Museum of Images of the Unconscious" in 1952. She questioned the neurological and physiological epistemology of mental disorders, advocating instead for a humanist and psychological approach to subjectivity, marking a shift from institutional psychiatry to psychopathology. We investigate how this change was made possible by Jungian psychoanalysis and art therapy, in which the Brazilian psychiatrist discovered alternative types of treatment targeted at understanding and treating mentally ill patients. In this way, we focus on her ability to incorporate culture as a way of expressing and managing subjective pain, especially in the case of schizophrenic patients.*

Keywords: *Nise da Silveira; art therapy; anti-asylum; psychiatry; Jung.*

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Introduction

Nise da Silveira was born in the north of Brazil, in Maceió, in 1905. She died in Rio de Janeiro in 1999, where she worked as a therapist and psychiatrist, making important contributions to Brazilian psychiatry. We would like to start this article with a gender issue that caught our attention when we began this brief investigation into Silveira: her importance and her erasure as a promising figure in the process of deinstitutionalizing psychiatric treatment in Brazil (Melo & Ferreira 2013). Much mention is given to the work of Franco Basaglia and Ronald David Laing, who were undoubtedly crucial to the anti-asylum movement in Brazil and other countries. However, before these doctors' influence in the country, Nise had already developed an anti-hospitalization therapeutic theory based on the free expression of individuals and their capacity for regeneration through art and other methods of subjective development.

There is not only a gender problem in the analysis of the history of psychiatry in 20th century in Brazil, but also an ethnocentric reading that prioritized “outside” influence as the sole factor capable of revolutionizing mental health. The importance of the dialogue with the European psychiatric field is undeniable, after all, Nise maintained contact with Jung and other European institutions (Nise 2023/1968, Magaldi 2020, Melo 2001). However, we would like to start this text by addressing this slight omission. Slight because Nise da Silveira was and is recognized as a transformative figure in psychiatry's relationship with culture and art. What is often overlooked is her pioneering role in the movement that challenged traditional psychiatry through art and other forms of rehabilitation as early as the 1940s (Melo 2001: 2009).

Nise da Silveira faced significant resistance throughout her professional career, whether because of gender issues or because she questioned the “standard” psychiatry of her time, which was predominantly male-dominated. Although she suffered constant retaliation from her colleagues, Silveira received support from important leaders in the field of mental health, who respected the positive results she achieved through creative rehabilitation without confinement. One of these conflicts was reported in the newspapers “Diário de notícias” (January 28, 1960) and “Correio da manhã” (January 31, 1960):

A few days ago, a crisis broke out at the Engenho de Dentro Psychiatric Center, which is part of the National Service for the Mentally Ill. It was caused by the abusive and rude attitude of the administrator, Mr. Fernandes. The case is that this lay official, taking advantage of the absence of Dr. Nise Magalhaes da Silveira, creator and director of the Oc-

cupational Therapeutics Service, on vacation at that time, removed from the Service and sent to the City Hall, for the purpose of sacrificing them, some dogs that the well-known psychiatrist kept at her expense. She considered contact with animals to be useful for the recovery and well-being of the mentally ill.

Surprised by the arbitrary and disrespectful act of the administrator, Dr. Nise da Silveira went to the director of the National Service for Mental Illness, Prof. Lopes Rodrigues. She asked for a transfer to another sector of the service, because the director of the CNP was unwilling or unable to revoke the abusive act of his bureaucratic subordinate (not a doctor).

[...]

[Nise:] "I confess that it is painful for me to leave the Occupational Therapy Section, a section that I have guided since its first steps. I am now handing it over with 19 sectors of activity: with a museum that has an important collection of artistic works by psychotic patients and which may even be, according to the opinion expressed in writing by Prof. Lopez Iber when he visited us in October 1956".²

A few days after her resignation, Nise da Silveira received a response refusing her request. The solution offered by the director of the National Service for Mental Illness was to keep Nise in her post, while removing the administrative official:

The director of the National Service for Mental Diseases, Prof. Lopes Rodrigues, in a letter to Dr. Nise da Silveira, refused to accept her request to resign as head of the Occupational Therapy Section at the National Psychiatric Center. Dr. Nise's request, as we know, and Correio da Manhã reported extensively on the case, was linked to the attitude of the administrator of the National Psychiatric Centre, Mr. Joaquim Fernandes. [...] The solution, therefore, has already been found, with Dr. Nise Silveira remaining head of the Occupational Therapy Section at the CPN, and the removal of the administrator who caused this situation.³

The work of the Brazilian psychiatrist represented an epistemological shift in Brazilian mental health, moving away from a biological and neurological approach to a more humanistic, psychopathological, and cultural approach. In this sense, Nise da Silveira believed that there was

² "Crisis at the National Psychiatric Center: Doctor Nise da Silveira leaves". *Diário de Notícias*, January 28, 1960. In: Images of the Unconscious Museum Collection. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

³ "Dr. Nise da Silveira kept in charge". *Correio da Manhã*, January 31, 1960. In: Images of the Unconscious Museum Collection. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

no separation between mind and body, rather these dimensions were integrated. Furthermore, she argued that diagnoses of psychosis (such as schizophrenia) did not diminish the creative capacities and emotions of those affected by the disorder. She pushed the boundaries of what was considered "madness", challenging psychiatry's approaches of exclusion and isolation of the psychotic subject. Silveira contended that psychosis was not capable of destroying an individual's subjectivity, even if it deviated from socially established norms. The narrative of "madness" was political, alienating, and hygienist, and Nise da Silveira tried her best to deconstruct this pervasive signifier in global psychiatry at the time.

This article aims to introduce foreign audiences to Nise da Silveira's thinking and work, using the history of psychiatry in Brazil and globally as a starting point, given that these discussions were not limited to South America. Our theoretical-methodological reading is inspired by Conrad's (2016) work on global history. Thus, our point of departure is to investigate a topic while considering not just the national context, but also the global linkages on issues that extend beyond the geographical area in which they existed. We will specifically examine the importance of culture, particularly its artistic dimension, in the treatment of mental diseases, as well as the epistemological challenge to psychiatry within a predominantly biological framework of mental suffering. In this way, we will explore aspects of a 20th century vigorous debate, which continues today in other forms: what is the role of culture in mental disorders and how can they be analyzed and treated beyond the neurobiological sphere?

Beyond biological psychiatry: electroshock, lobotomy, and insulin therapy

From the start of her career, Nise da Silveira began to move away from biological psychiatry towards psychology. She understood mental suffering within the realm of psychopathology, viewing it not exclusively as a biological and neurological issue, but as a symbolic one (Silveira 1952, 1966, 1981). At that time, the treatment of mental disorders relied on physical intervention methods, such as lobotomy, electroshock, and insulin therapy. Nise da Silveira interpreted them as forms of physical torture and refused to use them on psychotic patients.

During the Vargas dictatorship in Brazil, between 1937 and 1945, Nise da Silveira was imprisoned for her involvement with the Communist Party and Marxist ideas, including in the health field. From 1936 to 1944, she was removed from public service because of her ties to

“communism”⁴. In prison, she witnessed the effects of torture firsthand and criticized the method of Italian psychiatrist Ugo Cerletti. Cerletti had developed a method of inducing convulsions by giving electric shocks to pigs before they were slaughtered. At the time, schizophrenia was considered distinct from epilepsy, and provoking seizures was seen as a treatment for schizophrenic psychosis. This system, widely used throughout several decades of the 20th century, was strongly criticized by Nise, who believed it to be an ineffective strategy.

Nise reached these conclusions by opening up space for active listening to and understanding of the complaints of patients who had undergone lobotomy, electroshock or insulin therapy (Melo 2009, Nise 1952, 1966). She found that these treatments were ineffective for psychosis, such as schizophrenia. On the contrary, patients often worsened after undergoing these procedures.

Insulin therapy was used as a sedative in cases of *delirium tremens* as a way of causing hypoglycemia in people who were malnourished because they refused to eat. Neurophysiologist and psychiatrist Manfred Sakel (1900 – 1957), who created the insulin shock method, realized that this technique brought about improvements in patients with mental disorders who were sensitive to insulin. Since the 1930s, insulin therapy started to be applied mainly to patients with paranoid and catatonic schizophrenia. Nise da Silveira strongly opposed insulin therapy, as she did lobotomy and electroshock. Her critique of these methods led her to explore alternative treatments for psychosis and other disorders: art therapy and different forms of occupational therapy. According to Melo (2009: 35):

The aim of hypoglycemic shock, as well as electroshock, was to produce a profound alteration in the higher psychic functions. These alterations can indeed occur. Thus, the most apparent symptoms of the disease are suppressed, without, however, inducing a change in the “psychological background”. Nise da Silveira considered this type of proposal to be too risky and with too few results. So, after the person who had undergone insulin therapy regained consciousness, the doctor from Alagoas went to the director of the psychiatric center, Dr. Paulo Elejalde, and told him that she was not suitable to be a doctor. She asked to be given another job at the hospital. Paulo Elejalde suggested that she take over the Occupational Therapy Section of the Pedro II Psychiatric Center in Rio de Janeiro. Nise da Silveira commented: “There begins another stage of my

⁴ “Prisoners of 1935 recount their memories”. *Jornal do Brasil*, 24 July 1988, page 8. In: Nise da Silveira Archive / Images of the Unconscious Museum Collection. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

life. A beautiful stage in my work”. (SILVEIRA *apud* GULLAR, 1996: 45, translated by the authors).

In the Occupational Therapy Section of the Pedro II Psychiatric Center in Rio de Janeiro, Nise da Silveira put into practice her non-aggressive clinical method and her fight against physiological intervention procedures. One of the main targets of her fight was psychosurgery. From the 1930s onwards, lobotomy became popular in medical circles via the work of Egas Moniz (1874 – 1955), who used prefrontal leucotomies on people who complained of anxiety, depression, and schizophrenia (Melo 2009).

Nise followed the opposite path by establishing art, painting, and modeling studios, focusing on the creative capacity of patients with severe mental disorders (Silveira 1981, 1992). To prove the ineffectiveness and long-term sequelae of lobotomy, Nise da Silveira carried out an experiment with three patients: L.N., L., and A. She was unable to prevent them from undergoing lobotomy and concluded the experiment after the interventions were carried out. The Brazilian psychiatrist compared the artistic production of the patients before and after lobotomy and verified the devastating nature of psychosurgery. This work received national and international notoriety, appearing in Iracy Doyle’s article “Egas Moniz and the Spirit of Time”, and in Robert Volmat’s book “L’art Psychopathologique”, as well as in the article “La Création et la Lobotomie” (Melo 2009: 38). The sculptures made by the patient L.N. were presented at the First World Congress of Psychiatry in Paris (1950), and at the First Latin American Congress of Mental Health in São Paulo (1954) where Nise exhibited the works of L.N., L., and A. (Melo 2009).

After all, what conclusions did Nise reach with art therapy and other forms of occupational treatment? The Brazilian psychiatrist identified psychosurgery techniques as a means of erasing the subject and their emotions. The aim was to suppress “madness” and “abnormal” behavior, silencing the individual so they would fit in and not disturb the social order, whether in the family, the hospital environment, or society in general (Magaldi 2018). Silveira considered this technique to be a palliative and punitive measure to force patients to adapt to the social norm, rather than a treatment that embraced individuals with severe mental disorders. She proposed a methodology that promoted the expression of these patients’ emotions and subjectivity through art and creative power (Melo 2009: 2013). The social reintegration of Nise’s patients was achieved

through their unique self-expression, not through the silencing effects of lobotomy or electroshock.

Image 1: *Sculptures made by her patient L.N., showing his works before and after the lobotomy. Source: Collection of the Museum of Images of the Unconscious (photo taken by the authors)*

During the 1950s, lobotomy and electroshock began to be considered ineffective methods for treating severe disorders of the mind. This reassessment occurred, above all, with the advent of psychotropic drugs. The epistemological basis of psychiatry was still based on biologism and took little or no account of the psychosocial and symbolic autonomy of mental disorders. Although the technique changed (to psychotropics), the methodology remained the same: suppressing and silencing “abnormal” behavior and symptoms of suffering. According to Melo (2009: 39), Nise da Silveira's interpretation is different, “because she does not perceive the human being based on parts and does not see the mentally ill person, under any circumstances, as a bundle of symptoms. The human being, according to Nise da Silveira, must be understood in its totality and analyzed in all its complexity”.

Art, subjectivity, and occupational therapies: cultural methodologies in the treatment of schizophrenia and other mental disorders

The relationship between art and psychiatry dates back to the 19th century, but it was not until the 20th century that this combination was recognized as artistic expression, rather than simply as a manifestation of a mental disorder. In 1882, Cesare Lombroso (1835 – 1909) wrote the book “*Genio e Follia*”, analyzing the connection between artistic creation and mental illness. In Germany, through Kraepelin's work at the Heidelberg Hospital, an important collection of works created by psychiatric patients was established. One of the most in-depth analyses of the subject was produced by Hans Prinzhorn in 1922, based on the Heidelberg Hospital collection. According to Nise da Silveira,

Prinzhorn's main contribution in appreciating the plastic expression in the works of the ten authors presented in *Bildnerei der Geisteskranken*, which he described as monumental, was to have demonstrated "that a creative drive, a need for instinctive expression, survives the disintegration of the personality". (Melo 2009: 40, translated by the authors).

Nise da Silveira explored the creative drive of psychiatric patients in her occupational therapy atelier at the Pedro II Psychiatric Center. This spontaneity and expressiveness were also characteristic of the artistic and intellectual movements of the time: Modernism in the arts and the New School in education (Melo 2009). The drawings made by these patients had a spontaneous and peculiar content, yet aligned with some of the aesthetic and educational traits of the era. These individuals were able to produce authentic artwork and express their subjectivity without disconnecting from their social environment (Melo 2009). In this way, Nise da Silveira demonstrated that people with mental disorders were able to maintain a sense of self and engage with their social environment, even if their condition placed them in a state of a “disjointed self” (Silveira 1981, 1992).

For a foreign audience, it may be helpful to briefly explain the Modernist movement and the New School. Modernism in Brazil, particularly in the arts, aimed to break away from the elitist and colonial academicism of European and world art, introducing unique and transgressive elements that contrasted with the established models of painting of Western fine art academies. Hence, peripheral and less conventional references (such as the paintings of psychiatric patients) were recognized as

authentic and original expressions of art. There was also an appreciation of Brazilian references in the artistic sphere, whether through characters, shapes, or colors (Melo 2009).

The New School was a movement in the educational field that rethought teaching in general, breaking with the traditional and hierarchical way of transmitting knowledge. This approach placed the learner at the center of the pedagogical process, not as a recipient of knowledge, but as an active, unique, and creative participant in the educational process. The teacher does not preach wisdom, but rather takes the student on a collaborative and dynamic learning path, a stark contrast to traditional teaching methods.

Artistic modernism and the New School opened up a space for works of art outside the intellectualist norms of the time, especially those from Europe. The paintings made by psychiatric patients thus found space and appreciation in artistic and clinical circles during this period of aesthetic and educational transformation. The spontaneity of artistic expression was valued and, for this reason, paintings by psychiatric patients found their place in that context. Even though Nise da Silveira's art therapy was a novel psychiatric method at the time, it was connected with the national and worldwide pursuit of new approaches to address the relationship between culture and mental distress.

The emphasis on spontaneity in artistic expression in the field of psychiatry was a key element in the work carried out by Osório Cesar at the Juquery Psychiatric Hospital in São Paulo. Osório was an important author for Nise da Silveira, and his writings were important for the theoretical foundation of Silveira's works. Many of Osório's publications were found in Nise's collection, particularly those about creative expressions and psychoanalytical works, both of which were fundamental to their shared thinking.

Through his engagement with psychoanalysis, Osório valued the uniqueness of the artistic productions by psychiatric patients, publishing his book entitled "Primitive Art Among Asylum Patients" in 1925. He opposed the development of artistic models for patients to follow. On the contrary, he believed the role of art in psychiatric centers should be to cultivate the uniqueness and expressiveness of each individual. Only in this way could art take on a liberating function and help manage psychic suffering (Melo 2009). A preliminary version of this work was sent to Freud, thus strengthening the link with psychoanalysis.

Nise da Silveira corresponded with Osório Cesar and they shared a theoretical alignment regarding politico-clinical aspects. They both

sought to expand the limits of madness, viewing those outside the norm as individuals who, in some way, questioned capitalist society and the authoritarian regimes of their time, such as the Vargas dictatorship (1937 – 1945). They defended an epistemology of freedom, asserting that psychotics, contrary to psychiatric beliefs of the time, were individuals capable of self-expression, creativity and social engagement, though not necessarily in line with the capitalist way of being. They are individuals who do not see productivity as the ultimate value in life and who pursue alternative paths in society.

The fact is that “madness” subverted the social order and unsettled not only families but also the politics of bodily and behavioral regulation. Nise and Osório were united in valuing freedom of expression, including artistic expression, and in recognizing the ability of psychiatric patients to rehabilitate themselves through creative, active, and free practices in spaces outside of hospitals and beyond compulsory confinement. Nise da Silveira was arrested and persecuted during the Vargas dictatorship for her involvement with Marxist ideas and for her membership in the Communist Party⁵. During her imprisonment, she began to seriously question the effects of confinement on mental health, asking whether it was truly the best treatment for a patient with a mental disorder.

Osório Cesar, on the other hand, in addition to engaging with the same circles as Nise, visited Russia in the 1930s and served as a translator and interpreter of Pavlov’s work for the Brazilian audience. His alignment with the USSR was even more intense. However, what he did was to appropriate and reread Pavlov’s work, adapting it to the Latin American public without the biological excesses of Pavlovianism. It is hard to reconcile Osorio's contradiction in being both a promoter of artistic therapies and a critical reader of Pavlov at the same time. However, this was a common inconsistency for psychiatrists in that context, as they were torn between the methods of psychosurgery and alternative artistic and cultural therapies.

Psychoanalysis was introduced into Nise's thinking via Marxist ideas, especially through her dialogue with Brazilian neurologist Antônio Austregésilo (1876 – 1960). Nise graduated at a time when hygienism was a significant topic in medicine, yet followed a different path by combining psychoanalysis, art, and Marxism (Melo 2009: 2001). Psychoa-

⁵ “Prisoners of 1935 recount their memories”. *Jornal do Brasil*, 24 July 1988, page 8. In: Nise da Silveira Archive / Images of the Unconscious Museum Collection. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

nalysis was and still is widely criticized for placing all responsibility on the individual, especially through Oedipal mythology (Pires 2024). Contact with Marxist theories introduced into Nise da Silveira's work the importance of social factors in the development and management of mental disorders. She shifted the responsibility for their illness and even for their treatment away from the individual (Silveira 1966).

Art therapy: the patient as a creative subject

Nise da Silveira took over the coordination of the Occupational Therapy Section at the Pedro II Psychiatric Center in Rio de Janeiro in 1946. From then on, she was able to translate most of her theoretical perspectives into the clinical sphere. Nise's clinical practice was based not only on contact with Jungian psychoanalysis and art therapy (Frayze-Pereira 2003, Magaldi 2020), but also by a liberating approach towards psychotic subjects, recognizing their capacity to act creatively within the social environment, albeit not always in ways that aligned with capitalist expectations. It was a politically engaged clinic based on transforming society, and it was certainly inspired by Marxist ideas that were prevalent in Brazilian intellectual circles at the time.

In 1969, Nise da Silveira consolidated her Carl G. Jung Study Group, which had been operating informally since 1954. The meetings were open to professionals and non-specialists, not necessarily from the health field. (Magaldi 2020). It was a forum for, but not restricted to, the exchange and dissemination of Jung's knowledge. Nise re-interpreted Jung based on the Brazilian context and the socio-cultural problems the country faced, especially in the psychiatric environment. The group included a diverse mix of individuals from psychology, the arts, and other fields of knowledge. From 1965 onward, the group produced a journal called "Quaternio", the last edition of which was published in 2001, after Nise's death.

Nise da Silveira was invited by Jung to take part in the activities of his institute in 1957 in Zurich. Jung was interested in the artistic work produced by schizophrenic patients treated by Nise at the Occupational Therapy Atelier in Rio de Janeiro. The meeting was intended to encourage Silveira to attend classes, seminars and work directly with Jung's collaborators in order to prepare an exhibition of "psychopathological art" that would be shown at the International Congress of Psychiatry in Zurich that year.

Silveira was a pioneer in introducing Jung's thought to the Brazilian public in an accessible way, though she did not simply replicate ana-

lytical therapy. Although she never trained and joined Jung's group as a psychoanalyst, she maintained a relationship of exchange with them - a collaboration Jung himself desired, as expressed in the letter in which he invited the Brazilian psychiatrist: "I will be happy if, through the visit of Dr. Nise da Silveira, the contact between the psychiatrists of Brazil and Switzerland deepens. It will not be without importance for the future of both psychology and psychiatry. Signature and stamp: Prof. C. G. Jung"⁶.

Image 2: *Painting by patient A.G., 1971. Source: Collection of the Museum of Images of the Unconscious (photo taken by the authors)*

The recognition of art as a form of non-verbal communication – beyond the expression and revelation of subjectivities - and its use as a therapeutic resource emerged timidly at the end of the 19th century. Psychiatrist Nise da Silveira, distancing herself from the conventional methods of the time, which she viewed as aggressive and ineffective, adopted the method based on art and expressive activities as a therapeutic resource (Magaldi, 2020).

⁶ Letter of invitation from Carl Jung to Nise da Silveira (original in French), October 3, 1956. In: Nise da Silveira Archive / Museum of Images of the Unconscious. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

Image 3: *Painting by patient C.P., 1953.*

*Source: Collection of the Museum of Images of the Unconscious
(photo taken by the authors)*

Returning to the beginning of Nise's career in the Occupational Therapy Section, it is worth noting that even before the psychiatrist's arrival, some occupational activities were already taking place there, but they only focused on manual labor and cleaning services. Silveira was a pioneer in the use of art and the creation of an atelier for expressive activities, partnering with the artist Almir Mavignier, then an administrative employee at the hospital, to offer some manual activities such as painting, sculpture, and modeling. Both aimed to provide spontaneous art as an alternative to treatment, recognizing in that setting the importance of affection and interaction among the patients (Magaldi, 2018: 75). This spontaneous nature of the art produced by schizophrenic patients was described in a letter to Jung, in 1954, when Nise sent him some photographs of the work done by her patients:

Rio de Janeiro, November 12, 1954.

Professor C. G. Jung,

Master,

In the psychiatric center in Rio de Janeiro, there is, alongside other areas of activity in the therapeutic occupation service, an atelier where the patients draw and paint in complete freedom. No suggestions are given to them, and no models are proposed. And so, primordial images emerge in these paintings, bringing an empirical and convincing demonstration of analytical psychology.

With my most respectful homage, I am sending you some photographs of paintings that look like mandalas to me. They were painted by schizophrenics, spontaneously. Any possibility of cultural influence is ruled out.

I can't tell you, master, how much the study of your books has shed light on my work as a psychiatrist and how much they help me personally.

Please, believe me, your most humble disciple – Nise da Silveira.

Marquês de Abrantes, 151, ap. 403

Rio de Janeiro – Brazil – or nearby⁷

Nise's decision to oppose physical interventions and treatments of that period, such as lobotomies, electroshock, and insulin therapy, stemmed also from her critique of the assistential care model of the time. Art, also used as a tool for non-verbal communication, helped the psychiatrist to understand that subjectivity was not valued or recognized within the assistential model. As a result, the use of images became a means of accessing what Silveira called the “inner world” of her patients, bringing the notion of the unconscious to the forefront. In her work *Images of the Unconscious* (1981), a book that expresses and condenses Nise's thoughts, the author states that:

Psychoanalysis tries to discover disguised repressed material in painted images. In order to bring them to consciousness, in analytical therapy the image will only serve as a starting point for verbal associations until the repressed unconscious contents are reached. ... It will therefore be necessary for the images to be translated into words. (Silveira 1981: 133-134, translated by the authors).

Nevertheless, according to Silveira (1981), it would be possible to observe directly and without the mediation of words the expression of the unconscious through images.

⁷ Letter from Nise da Silveira to Jung, November 12, 1954. In: Nise da Silveira Archive / Museum of Images of the Unconscious. Original in Portuguese, translated by the authors.

Jung – the founder of analytical psychology – was one of the sources of great inspiration for the psychiatrist from Alagoas (Silveira 2023/1968). Carl Jung's main theory, known as the *archetypes* and the *collective unconscious*, proposed the existence of a layer even deeper than the so-called personal unconscious. In the collective unconscious are deposited matrices of images, the archetypes, which have been delineated throughout human evolution. Through her engagement with Jung's ideas and other influences, Nise was able to argue that the creation of images not only served as a way to access the unconscious, but also acted as a catalyst for therapeutic effectiveness (Magaldi, 2018).

Silveira also argued that descriptive psychopathology - which involves the precise description and categorization of abnormal experiences, observable symptoms and behavioral phenomena – was insufficient to convey the full extent of these experiences. As a result, Nise did not limit herself to the prevalent diagnostic systems of her time. She considered "madness" as more than just symptoms, and directly opposed the psychiatric therapies and diagnostic systems of her era.

Silveira avoided using the terms "illness" or "schizophrenia", preferring the idea of a "state of being", attributing this re-reading of "madness" and its modes of expression to Antonin Artaud. Artaud was a French writer and playwright, known for his famous *Cahiers*, in which he recorded his experiences in Parisian psychiatric hospitals, where he spent the last years of his life. Thus, "such symptoms do not constitute a disease, a defined pathological entity, but manifest themselves as multiple states of dismemberment and transformation of being" (Silveira 1989: 9; Magaldi 2018: 78).

Nise's thought and desire to understand madness in a unique way, avoiding the division between body and mind, aligns with the postulates of Occupational Therapy (OT) in the study of mental disorders and the unconscious. Understanding the subject in its entirety is a central tenet of the OT profession today, which values a holistic view of human beings.

Nise was one of the main figures to consolidate the humanist model of OT from the 1940s onwards. From this perspective, the primary goal of art and other activities was to allow unconscious images to be expressed. This type of art therapy used the therapeutic space – for Silveira this space was the Occupational Therapy section at the Psychiatric Center in Engenho de Dentro – as a laboratory for studying the images of the unconscious (Almeida 2010).

It is crucial to emphasize the relevance of the Brazilian psychiatrist's work in breaking with the organicist paradigm of the time, recog-

nizing patients' subjectivity in order to encourage changes based on interaction with the social environment, ultimately reducing the suffering of psychotic patients.

Conclusion

The 20th century was a time when the discussion about the intertwining of culture and mental health became a global and important agenda. However, it was during the second half of the 20th century that this topic was tackled in greater depth and it was then that it achieved its first results in the process of questioning psychiatry's biologizing paradigm. The establishment of asylums and hospitalization with no prospects for social reintegration reflected an overly biological approach characteristic of medicine at that time. In this sense, Nise da Silveira's work with art therapy and other ways of managing disorders of the mind was pioneering in the Brazilian and even global context, given the late development of the anti-asylum movement in the second half of the 20th century.

Silveira faced several barriers in establishing herself as a psychiatrist and therapist at a time when medicine was extremely masculine and followed perspectives she opposed. There is a gender issue, as we discussed at the beginning of the article, but also a clash of narratives: the introduction of the symbolic field into psychiatry and treatment, and the development of a psychopathology that incorporated subjective and social elements. Opposing the traditional methods of the time led to rivalries and resistance within the medical field, although she was welcomed by other professionals and leaders of the health system. It is interesting to note that, although Silveira was mentioned, she did not become a central figure in the narrative of the anti-asylum movement in Brazil. She proposed clinical methods that perhaps sounded absurd at the time, and her anti-asylum agenda predated the Brazilian movement itself, which began in the late 1970s.

This pioneering spirit placed her in an "outsider" position within her context, resulting in delayed recognition. Today, her work certainly represents a significant development in the field of psychiatry and OT in Brazil and she is recognized by health professionals (psychiatrists, occupational therapists, psychologists) as a prominent figure in the history of national and international mental health. This silencing of the past says a lot about the narrowing of psychiatry's focus onto methods of physical intervention, from lobotomy to the psychotropic drugs that now dominate the mental health market.

For Nise, the alternative was to find ways within culture and the symbolism (of images) to manage psychic suffering and severe disorders such as schizophrenia. She was often seen as a “rebellious psychiatrist”. This rebelliousness, however, was not simply a personality trait of hers. It was a defiant medical-political stance grounded in a symbolic epistemology of psychopathology which saw the “disturbed subject” as free and creative. The psychotic patient was capable of existing in the social environment in ways that defied the dictates of capitalist and productivist society, and their rehabilitation could not be a total adaptation to “normality”. The artistic capacity of individuals diagnosed with “schizophrenia” (which she called a “state of being” so as not to reduce the patient to their disorder) did not come exclusively from their “illness”. It reflected their inherent creativity and subjectivity, even if their behavior was “abnormal” (outside the norm) in some respects.

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